

Literature Review from Different Approaches to Cognitive- Behavioral Therapy

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Abstract

Cognitive-behavioral therapy, or CBT for short, is a term used to describe a group of therapeutic approaches combined with the fundamental concept that mental illness and psychological suffering are sustained by cognitive variables. This therapeutic method, pioneered by Beck (1970) and Ellis (1962), is based on the basic idea that maladaptive cognitions lead to the persistence of emotional disturbance and behavioral disorders. According to the paradigm developed by Beck, these dissonant cognitions include broad ideas about the world, self, and future, also known as schemas. These schemas give rise to specific and automatic thinking in certain situations. According to the basic model, changes in the client's emotional distress and problematic behaviors are the direct result of therapy procedures aimed at changing maladaptive thought patterns. Since these early formulations, several disorder-specific CBT protocols have been set up. This disorder-specific CBT protocols specifically target different cognitive and behavioral care variables associated with various disorders. Although there are significant differences in some of the specific treatment procedures involved in the treatment protocols specific to this disorder, they all adhere to the same basic concept and take a similarly comprehensive approach to treatment. Reduction of symptoms, improvement of functioning and improvement of condition are overarching goals of therapy

according to the model of medical psychiatry used to guide treatment. The patient must be an active participant in a collaborative problem-solving process to achieve this goal. This will allow the patient to evaluate and discuss the validity of maladaptive cognitions and change maladaptive behavioral patterns. Thus, contemporary cognitive behavioral therapy refers to a family of therapies that include a set of strategies that focus on one's emotions, behaviors, and thoughts (for example, Hofmann, 2011; Hofmann, Asmundson, & Beck, in press). Although these approaches place an emphasis on cognitive aspects, physiological, emotional, and behavioral aspects are also recognized for the role they play in the persistence of the disorder.

Keywords: *Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, Therapies in Psychology, Clinical Psychology, CBT, Cognitive Therapy, Behavioral Therapy*

1. Introduction

In a recent study analyzing CBT meta-analyses, researchers found that there were assessments covering sixteen different diseases or populations (Butler, Chapman, Forman, & Beck, 2006). This was the first study of meta-analytical studies that we are aware of examining the effectiveness of CBT for a variety of different psychiatric problems. Since its first publication, this article has become one of the most important criticisms of the CIS. On the other hand, the search approach was extremely limited because only a single meta-analysis was chosen to be each disease. In addition, the research was only conducted until 2004, although a considerable number of reviews were published in later years. In fact, the vast majority, or 84%, of the research was not published until 2004. Evidence base supporting the effectiveness of CBT. All meta-analyses considered for inclusion in this study were found to adhere to proper methodological standards.

269 meta-analyses have been grouped together and organized into categories to give the most relevant and comprehensive analysis possible of the effectiveness of CBT across various problem areas and research populations . The following conditions are divided into main categories:

1. *substance use disorder,*
2. *Schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders*

3. *depression and dysthymia,*
4. *bipolar disorder,*
5. *anxiety disorders,*
6. *somatoform disorders,*
7. *Eating disorders,*
8. *Insomnia,*
9. *personality disorders,*
10. *anger and aggression,*
11. *criminal behavior,*
12. *general stress,*
13. *general medical conditions,*
14. *Chronic pain and fatigue*
15. *pregnancy complications and female hormonal conditions.*

In addition, the use of CBT in the treatment of problems in children and the elderly has been the focus of various meta-analyses. For each disease and demographic grouping, a qualitative description of the data was provided, considering the results of each meta-analysis conducted on that population .

2. **Addiction and Substance Use Disorders**

There was evidence that cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) was effective in treating marijuana addiction. There was also evidence that multi-session CBT was more effective than single-session CBT or other shorter interventions and had a lower dropout rate compared to control conditions (Dutra et al., 2008). However, the effect size of CBT was low compared to the effect sizes of other psychosocial interventions (such as probability management, relapse prevention, and motivational approaches) for substance abuse. On the other hand, agonist treatments showed a larger effect size

than CBT in some drug addictions, such as opioid and alcohol addiction (Powers, Vedel, & Emmelkamp, 2008).

Findings of treatments for smoking cessation found that coping skills based in part on CBT techniques were highly effective in reducing relapse in a sample of nicotine quitting populations (Song, Huttunen-Lenz, & Holland, 2010). In addition, a different meta-analysis found that CBT (alone or in combination with nicotine replacement therapy) was superior to nicotine replacement therapy alone (Garcia-Vera & Sanz, 2006). There is also evidence that behavioral techniques are more effective than control therapies in treating problem gambling . This contrasts with conventionally accepted treatments (Oakley-Browne et al., 2000). A meta-analysis (Leung and Cottler, 2009) reported larger effect sizes of CBT when grouped with other non-pharmacological treatments (such as brief interventions) compared to pharmacological agents (such as naltrexone, carbamazepine, and topiramate). However, the CBT was no more effective than these shorter and cheaper approaches.

3. Schizophrenia and Other Disorders of the Psychotic Spectrum

Several meta-analyses investigating the effectiveness of psychological therapies for schizophrenia have found that cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) has a positive effect on positive symptoms of schizophrenia such as delusions and/or hallucinations (eg , Gould et al., 2001; Rector & Beck, 2001) . There is also evidence that cognitive behavioral therapy is a particularly promising addition to pharmacotherapy for schizophrenic patients suffering from an acute episode of psychosis rather than a more chronic condition (eg , Zimmerman et al., 2005). This applies to patients diagnosed with schizophrenia.

therapies such as early intervention programs or family intervention (eg, Bird et al, 2010; Alvarez-Jimenez et al, 2011), cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) has proven to have negligible effect on relapse or hospitalization. However, cognitive behavioral therapy had a positive effect on secondary outcomes. For example, a more recent meta-analysis conducted by Wykes, and colleagues (2008) examined controlled trials of CBT for schizophrenia. This meta-analysis

confirmed the findings from earlier meta-analyses (eg, Gould et al., 2001; Rector & Beck, 2001), with small to medium effect sizes of CBT compared to control conditions on both positive and negative. claimed it was. In addition, the findings of this meta-analysis showed that effect sizes for improvements in secondary outcomes that were not the primary goal of therapy , such as general functioning, mood, and social anxiety, were moderate.

4. Conditions such as Depression and Dysthymia

has been shown to be more successful in treating depression than control states, such as waiting listing or no therapy . The effect size of this finding was moderate (Van Straten, Geraedts, Verdonck-de Leeuw, Andersson, & Cuijpers, 2010; Beltman, Oude Voshaar, & Speckens, 2010). However, research comparing CBT with other active therapies, such as psychodynamic therapy, problem-solving therapy , and interpersonal psychotherapy, has produced mixed findings. These studies have shown that CBT is more effective than other active joint therapies. Meta-analyses have revealed that cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is as successful as other psychological therapies (for example, Beltman, Oude Voshaar, & Speckens, 2010; Cuijpers, Smit, Bohlmeijer, Hollon, & Andersson, 2010; Pfeiffer, Heisler , Piette, Rogers). and Valenstein, 2011). On the other hand, the findings of other studies revealed that CBT is effective (e.g., Di Giulio, 2010; Jorm, Morgan, & Hetrick, 2008; Tolin, 2010). For example, Jorm et al. (2008) discovered that post-treatment cognitive behavioral therapy is more effective than relaxing approaches. In addition, Tolin (2010) showed that cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) was superior to psychodynamic therapy both after treatment and at six-month follow-up, although this result only occurred when depression and anxiety symptoms were present.

exhibited comparable benefits on persistent depression symptoms with moderate to broad effect sizes . This was compared with the effects that pharmacological treatments had (Vos, Haby, Barendregt, Kruijshaar, Corry, & Andrews, 2004). According to the findings of earlier research, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) may receive help from inclusion of medication; more precisely, combination therapy consisting of CBT and pharmacotherapy was more successful than CBT alone (Chan, 2006).

5. Bipolar disorder

cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) for the treatment of bipolar illness showed that the overall effect sizes of post-treatment CBT were moderate to moderate, with benefits diminishing upwards during follow-up. These discoveries arose because of research into manic and depressive symptoms associated with bipolar illness (eg , Gregory, 2010a, 2010b). There is little evidence to support the use of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) as primary therapy in the treatment of bipolar illness, as opposed to its use as an adjunct to medication .

Some meta-analyses have focused on the effectiveness of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) for preventing relapse in bipolar patients, in addition to investigating the effectiveness of CBT for reducing the symptoms of bipolar patients. In a study by Beynon et al. (2008), cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) was shown to be successful in preventing relapse when compared to usual treatment. The study investigated the effectiveness of CBT in preventing relapse. Overall, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) for the treatment of bipolar illness has proven to be an effective way to prevent or delay relapses (eg , Lam, Burbeck, Wright, & Pilling, 2009; Çakır & Özerdem, 2010). In addition, the number of manic or depressive episodes in the past did not seem to have any effect on the efficacy of CBT in preventing relapses.

therapy , sometimes known as CBT , is a type of psychotherapy that teaches patients how to recognize and change unhelpful or distressing thought patterns that have a detrimental effect on both their actions and emotions.

6. Definition of CIS

"Cognitive behavioral therapy " refers to "psychotherapy that combines cognitive therapy with behavioral therapy by identifying mistaken or maladaptive patterns of thought, emotional response, or behavior and replacing them with desired patterns of thought, emotional response, or behavior."

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cognitive behavioral therapy is to replace the negative, irrational beliefs that arise on autopilot that can both contribute to and worsen our emotional problems, sadness, and anxiety. These unwanted unpleasant ideas that come to us suddenly can affect our mood badly.

cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), faulty thought patterns can be recognized, questioned, and eventually replaced with more objective and truthful ideas.

cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) refers to a variety of methods and strategies that target our ideas, emotions, and actions. Structured psychotherapies and self-help activities are examples of such interventions.

Primary focus of cognitive therapy is to recognize dysfunctional thinking processes, emotional responses, and behaviors and then work to correct or change them.

Dialectical Behavior Therapy, commonly known as DBT, is a type of talk therapy that combines many therapeutic techniques such as emotional regulation and mindfulness to heal harmful or distressing ideas and actions .

According to the concept of multimodal therapy, psychological problems need to be addressed by focusing on seven different but interrelated modalities:

behavior , emotion, sensation, imagery, cognition, interpersonal variables, and drug/biological considerations.

Finding irrational ideas is the first step in the rational emotional behavior therapy (REBT) process. The second step is to actively question these beliefs and the third step is to learn to recognize and change these thought patterns.

cognitive behavioral therapy each take a slightly different approach, the common goal of all of them is to address the underlying thought patterns that lead to psychological pain.

7. Techniques

is just one aspect of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). It uses a wide variety of ways to help individuals break free from these routines.

It is important for the person to understand how their ideas, feelings, and circumstances affect their maladaptive actions. However, this process can be challenging, especially for those who have difficulties with self-reflection. On the other hand, taking the time to recognize these ideas can lead to a journey of self-discovery and the provision of insights crucial to the therapy process. People typically learn new abilities in the context of cognitive behavioral therapy that can be applied to real-world conditions. For example, a person with a drug use problem may practice new coping skills and rehearse strategies to avoid or deal with social situations that have the potential to trigger relapse. They can also think about and write down triggers they have experienced in the past.

8. Goal Setting

Setting goals can be a crucial step in recovery from mental illness because it can help make changes that improve both health and life. When individuals engage in cognitive behavioral therapy, they run the risk of meeting several potential challenges.

9. Cognitive Model of Mental Illness

The cognitive model of mental illness, first created by Beck, serves as the basis for cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) (1964). The cognitive model, in its most basic version, assumes that people's emotions and behaviors are influenced by their perceptions of events occurring in their lives. ("Which Type Of Therapy Is Based On Learning Theory?") It is not a scenario that decides how people will feel; rather, it is the way individuals understand a situation that makes all the difference (Beck, 1964). In other words, how individuals perceive events is the primary determinant, not how they feel about events. For example, those suffering from depression are thought to have an extremely pessimistic view of how events should be interpreted (Beck, 1976). The way cognition is conceptualized, the way we think about things, as well as the essence of those

thoughts, is an important part of the cognitive model. Beck (1976) defined three stages of cognitive functioning as follows:

- a. *core beliefs*
- b. *Assumptions that do not work properly*
- c. *Constantly critical and demoralizing ideas*

10. Challenges Occurring in the "Here and Now"

CBT puts emphasis on the present moment while approaching its treatment with a problem-focused approach. Unlike some other talk therapies, this therapy focuses on difficulties that occur in the "here and now". It looks to find strategies to improve the patient's current state of mind, rather than focusing on the causes of discomfort or symptoms that have occurred in the patient's history . Goal setting is an integral part of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). It is important that the goals are "SMART", which means specific , measurable, achievable, realistic and time bound. One of the goals of treatment for a patient diagnosed with obsessive compulsive disorder may be to reduce the time they spend washing their hands from 5 hours a day to 1 hour a day at the end of the first three weeks. In deconstructing a challenge and creating a more manageable hierarchy of goals, the therapist aids the patient in placing goals in the proper order of importance. Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) sessions are designed to maximize the effectiveness of treatment, enhance the learning process, and focus therapeutic efforts on specific problems and workable solutions. The first step in each session is a process called agenda setting, in which the therapist collaborates with the patient to find activities that have the potential to lead to productive therapeutic work in that session. In addition, patients are given homework to do outside of therapy sessions to reinforce their understanding of CBT ideas as well as take their efforts beyond the constraints of the session .

CBT is both an organized and time-limited therapy . CBT treatment usually consists of five to twenty sessions, depending on the severity of the patient's anxiety or depression. Because of the survival, persistent nature of these diseases, and the slower progression documented by CBT,

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treatment may need to be extended if axis II disorders are present. Axis II disorders include personality disorders and mental disorders.

cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is to influence a person's behavior and thinking processes. Therefore, CBT applies both cognitive and behavioral approaches to treatment. The specific interventions used are decided in part by the formulation of the individual.

"Guided exploration" is an important cognitive part of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) (Padesky, 1993). This is a therapeutic position that requires trying to understand the patient's perspective on events and helping them expand their thinking to become aware of their underlying assumptions and explore alternative views and answers for themselves. Socratic inquiry is a type of inquiry that is an element of guided discovery. This type of questioning is rooted in the way Socrates (ca. 400 BC) helped his students reach a conclusion without explicitly telling what that conclusion was. According to Padesky (1993), the purpose of Socratic questioning is to direct the patient's attention to a subject unrelated to the subject he is currently focusing on. The use of questions by therapists allows them to probe a patient's assumptions, question the reasons and facts that support the patient's views, highlight alternative viewpoints, and explore reflections. For example, "What else can we assume?", "Why do you think ...? ", "What diverse ways are there to look at this?" and "Why... is it important ?" are all examples. are questions that can be asked. All the therapies that focus on each different level of cognition have guided exploration.

Recent innovations in behavior modification have often strayed around the role of cognitive processes in producing and alleviating symptomatology. Although self-reports of specific experiences cannot be verified by other observers, these introspective data supply several testable hypotheses.

Systematic examination of self-reports shows that an individual's belief systems, expectations, and assumptions have a strong influence on well-being as well as their directly observable behavior. By applying a cognitive model, the clinician can usefully interpret neurotic behavior in terms of the patient's idiosyncratic concepts about himself and his animate and inanimate environment. An individual's belief systems can be highly contradictory; that is, it can simultaneously rely on both realistic and unrealistic conceptualizations of the same event or object. This inconsistency in

beliefs may explain, for example, why an individual may react with fear to a harmless situation despite accepting that fear is unrealistic. (“(PDF) Cognitive behavioral therapy - ResearchGate”)

Cognitive therapy, based on cognitive theory, is designed to change an individual's idiosyncratic, maladaptive thinking. The basic cognitive technique consists of describing the individual's specific misconceptions, distortions, and maladaptive assumptions and evaluating their validity and plausibility. (“Cognitive Therapy: Nature and Relation to Behavior Therapy ...”) By loosening the grip of his persistent, distorted thinking, the patient can formulate his experiences more realistically. Clinical experience and some experimental studies show that this type of cognitive restructuring leads to symptom relief.

Considering the number of publications/studies, academic programs and/or practicing professionals, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is the gold standard in the psychotherapy field. Recently, however, some colleagues have debated pluralism in psychotherapy, questioning the gold standard status of CBT in psychotherapy because many studies are of low quality and/or benchmarking conditions are poor (eg, active comparators), thereby raising CBT's prominent status among academic programs and practitioners. defiant.

11. Gold Standard

We think that many issues are influential in the definition of the gold standard. If the gold standard is defined as the best we can have in this field, then, in fact, the CBT is not the gold standard and, as a progressive research program, the CBT does not currently argue for such status. However, if the gold standard is defined as the best we currently have in the field, then we argue that the CBT is indeed the gold standard.

In this article it is necessary to discuss that CBT is the gold standard psychological treatment – the best standard we have in the field currently available, for the following reasons:

(1) CBT is the most researched form of psychotherapy.

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- (2) *No other form of psychotherapy has been shown to be systematically superior to CBT; If there are systematic differences between psychotherapies, they usually prefer CBT.*
- (3) *are compatible with current mainstream human mind and behavior paradigms (eg, information processing).*

At the same time, there is clear room for further improvement, both in terms of the effectiveness/effectiveness of CBT and its underlying theories/mechanisms of change. It is also necessary to advocate for an integrated scientific psychotherapy in which CBT serves as the basic platform for integration .

Modern CBT is an umbrella term for empirically supported treatments for clearly defined psychopathologies targeted with specific treatment strategies. More recently, CBT has included a more trans-diagnostic/process-based and personalized approach with the goal of relating the therapeutic technique to the process and the individual client. Traditionally, clinical trials examining the efficacy of CBT have included waiting list control, placebo conditions, usual therapy/TAU, and other alternative treatments (including psychodynamic therapies and pharmacotherapies).

While several CBT studies have weak comparisons (for example, waiting list control conditions), there are many studies that meet stringent standards that compare CBT with strong comparison conditions (for example, pill or psychological placebo, TAU, other psychotherapies, pharmacotherapy). Indeed, Cuijpers et al. found that approximately 54% of the total trials for depression (approximately thirty-four trials) and approximately 20% (approximately 25) of the total anxiety trials met the criteria (ie, pill placebo or TAU) for a strong comparison. Cuijpers et al . also reported that 17% of the total studies for depression and anxiety were of high quality, and the correlation between the quality of CBT studies and effect sizes was not strong. Most psychotherapies do not even come close to these numbers in terms of comparator active status and quality of work, with the exception, for example, of interpersonal therapy for depression only, which has similar numbers . Compared to TAU or various active conditions, CBT is small/medium (for TAU) or small/ineffective (for active conditions). In these circumstances, however , even a

small effect size may be clinically especially important, depending on whether it is cumulative (eg, time and/or population) as well as cost and benefit analyzes .

12. Model Theorizes It Will Affect Our Overall Quality of Life

The cognitive behavioral model theorizes that the way we think, and act will affect our emotional and physical health and therefore our overall quality of life. The relationships between cognitions, behaviors, emotions, and physical responses are all considered bidirectional. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) is a talk therapy that looks to find and challenge maladaptive thoughts and behaviors, trying to develop diverse ways of thinking and acting to improve psychological and physical outcomes for patients. CBT has a set of core competencies that can be applied transdiagnostically; however, it is specifically designed for use in certain populations , such as CBT insomnia. Most CBTs are delivered by health issue-specific CBT process guidelines. It is correct to define high intensity as formal CBT in which a CBT-trained healthcare professional is presented in a face-to-face individual or group format. Low-intensity interventions focus on patient self-help and can be delivered by healthcare professionals with little to very extensive CBT training and through a variety of platforms (internet, telephone, and paper-based). This distinction may become less pronounced in some forms of CBT, called 'mixed care' , where high-intensity therapy is combined with low-intensity self-help methods.

13. Health-Related Quality of Life

Activity scheduling and graded task assignment aim to improve functioning and systematically increase pleasurable or productive experiences. (“The key principles of cognitive behavioural therapy”) Event planning is used to plan each day in advance. The therapist and patient work to reduce the stack of tasks to a manageable list that cuts the need for repetitive decision making. Graded task assignments create manageable steps to help overcome procrastination and anxiety-provoking situations. These techniques involve obtaining a baseline of activities for a day or week, grading activities by degree of ability and/or enjoyment, and then collaboratively designing

changes that will reactivate the patient, induce a greater sense of pleasure in life, or change behavior patterns. These techniques help patients re-establish their daily routines, increase pleasurable activities, and deal with problems and difficult issues by increasing problem solving. (“The key principles of cognitive behavioural therapy”) Behavior experiments are mostly used in anxiety-based mental health disorders. The technique allows a person to evaluate their predictions about disaster (for example, 'Something terrible will happen if I leave the house'). At the same time, behavioral experiments help patients learn to tolerate anxiety. Before completing a task, the patient makes a prediction and then records whether that prediction has come true. Over time, patients will reassess their thinking about the disaster, developing useful evidence against their predictions. The therapist collaborates with the client to develop hierarchical tasks, from the lowest anxiety to the higher anxiety tasks. The effectiveness of CBT has been evaluated in randomized control studies (RCTs) synthesized in systematic reviews of a wide range of physical and mental health problems, from schizophrenia⁴ to low back pain.

This overview will explore the effects of CBT on all health problems, in all populations and in all settings. The primary outcome would be health-related quality of life (HRQL) to capture the broader, general, biopsychosocial impact of CBT in addition to its impact on specific functional outcomes.

14. Conclusion

Finally, it found eleven studies that compared response rates between CBT and other treatments or control conditions. In seven of these reviews, CBT showed higher response rates than the comparator conditions, and only one review (Leichsenring & Leibig, 2003) conducted by the psychodynamically oriented authors reported that CBT had lower response rates than the comparator treatments. In summary, our review of meta-analytical studies examining the efficacy of CBT has shown that this therapy is used for a wide variety of psychological problems. Overall, the evidence base for CBT is extraordinarily strong and particularly for the treatment of anxiety disorders. However, despite the enormous literature base, there is still a clear need for high-quality studies examining the effectiveness of CBT. Also, the effectiveness of CBT for some problems is

questionable, suggesting that further improvement in CBT strategies is still needed. Additionally, most meta-analytical studies included studies with small sample sizes or insufficient control groups. In addition, meta-analytical studies of CBT on specific subgroups such as ethnic minorities and low-income samples have not been reported, except for children and elderly populations . Despite these weaknesses in some areas, the evidence base for CBT is overwhelming. Given the high cost-effectiveness of the intervention, it is surprising that many countries, including many developed countries, have yet to adopt CBT as a first-line intervention for mental disorders. A notable exception is the UK's National Health Commission's initiative to Improve Access to Psychological Therapies (Rachman & Wilson, 2008). It would be fair to believe that the time has come for others to follow suit.

15. References

- Babcock JC, Green CE, Robie C. Does batterers' treatment work? A meta-analytic review of domestic violence treatment. *Clinical Psychology Review*. 2004;23:1023–1053.
- Baker GA, Brooks JL, Goodfellow L, Bodde N, Aldenkamp A. Treatments for non-epileptic attack disorder. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2007;1:CD006370.
- Ballesio A, Aquino M, Feige B, et al. "The effectiveness of behavioral and cognitive behavioral therapies for insomnia on depressive symptoms: a systematic review and network meta-analysis." ("Effectiveness of cognitive-behavioural therapy for post-disaster ...") ("The effectiveness of behavioral and cognitive behavioral therapies ...") *Sleep Med Rev* 2018;37:114–29. doi:10.1016/j.smrv.2017.01.006
- Barsky AJ, Ahern DK. Cognitive-behavior therapy for hypochondriasis: a randomized controlled trial. *JAMA*. 2004;291:1464–70.
- Beck AT. Cognitive therapy: Nature and relation to behavior therapy. *Behavior Therapy*. 1970;1:184–200. []
- Beck BD, Hansen ÅM, Gold C. Coping with work-related stress through guided imagery and music: randomized controlled trial. *J Music Ther*. 2015;52:323–52.
- Beltman MW, Oude Voshaar RC, Speckens AE. Cognitive-behavioural therapy for depression in people with a somatic disease: meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *The*

- British Journal of Psychiatry. 2010;197:11–19.
- Beynon S, Soares-Weiser K, Woolacott N, Duffy S, Geddes JR. Psychosocial interventions for the prevention of relapse in bipolar disorder: systematic review of controlled trials. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*. 2008;192:5–11.
- Binks C, Fenton M, McCarthy L, Lee T, Adams CE, Duggan C. Psychological therapies for people with borderline personality disorder. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2006;1:CD005652.
- Bird V, Premkumar P, Kendall T, Whittington C, Mitchell J, Kuipers E. Early intervention services, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and family intervention in early psychosis: systematic review. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*. 2010;197:350–356. [PMC free article]
- Bisson J, Andrew M. Psychological treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2008;3:CD003388.
- Bisson JI, Ehlers A, Matthews R, Pilling S, Richards D, Turner S. Psychological treatments for chronic post-traumatic stress disorder. Systematic review and meta-analysis. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*. 2007;190:97–104.
- Bledsoe SE, Grote NK. Treating depression during pregnancy and the postpartum: A preliminary meta-analysis. *Research on Social Work Practice*. 2006;16:109–120. []
- "Brasure M, Fuchs E, MacDonald R, et al. Psychological and behavioral interventions for managing insomnia disorder: an evidence report for a clinical practice guideline by the american college of physicians." ("For Clinicians | Sleep and Sleep Disorders | CDC") ("For Clinicians | Sleep and Sleep Disorders | CDC") *Ann Intern Med* 2016;165:113–24.doi:10.7326/M15-1782
- Burns AM, Erickson DH, Brenner CA. Cognitive-behavioral therapy for medication-resistant psychosis: a meta-analytic review. *Psychiatr Serv* 2014;65:874–80.doi:10.1176/appi.ps.201300213 CrossRefPubMed
- Busse JW, Montori VM, Krasnik C, Patelis-Siotis I, Guyatt GH. "Psychological intervention for premenstrual syndrome: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials." ("Psychological intervention for premenstrual syndrome: A meta-analysis ...") ("Women-centered psychological intervention for premenstrual distress") *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics*. 2009;78:6–15.
- Chambless DL, Hollon SD. Defining empirically supported theories. *J Consult Clin Psychol* (1998) 66(1):7–18. doi:10.1037/0022-006X.66.1.7

- "Cheatle MD. Biopsychosocial approach to assessing and managing patients with chronic pain. " ("A Biopsychosocial Model-Based Clinical Approach in Myofascial Pain ...") ("Pain Management Center – Chapter 1 - International Association for ...") Med Clin North Am. 2016;100:43–53.
- Cherkin DC, Sherman KJ, Balderson BH, Cook AJ, Anderson ML, Hawkes RJ, et al. Effect of mindfulness-based stress reduction vs cognitive behavioral therapy or usual care on back pain and functional limitations in adults with chronic low back pain: a randomized clinical trial. JAMA. 2016;315:1240–9.
- Cludius B, Landmann S, Rose N, Heidenreich T, Hottenrott B, Schröder J, et al. Long-term effects of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy in patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder and residual symptoms after cognitive behavioral therapy: twelve-month follow-up of a randomized controlled trial. Psychiatry Res. 2020;291:113–9.
- Cochrane library. Cochrane reviews. [<https://www.cochranelibrary.com/>] Accessed 15 June 2021.
- Cormac I, Jones C, Campbell C. Cognitive behavior therapy for schizophrenia. Cochrane Database Syst Rev 2002;1:CD000524.
- Cuijpers P, Cristea IA, Karyotaki E, Reijnders M, Huibers MJ. How effective are cognitive behavior therapies for major depression and anxiety disorders? A meta-analytic update of the evidence. World Psychiatry (2016) 15(3):245–58. doi:10.1002/wps.20346
- Cuijpers P, Donker T, Weissman MM, Ravitz P, Cristea IA. Interpersonal psychotherapy for mental health problems: a comprehensive meta-analysis. Am J Psychiatry (2016) 173:680–7. doi:10.1176/appi.ajp.2015.1509141
- Cuijpers P, Turner EH, Koole SL, van Dijke A, Smit F. What is the threshold for a clinically relevant effect? The case of major depressive disorders. ("What is the threshold for a clinically relevant effect? the case of ...") ("What is the threshold for a clinically relevant effect? the case of ...") Depress Anxiety (2014) 31:374–8. doi:10.1002/da.22249
- Dimidjian, S., Hollon, S., Dobson, K., Schmaling, K., Kohlenberg, R., Addis, M., ... Jacobson, N. (2006) Randomized trial of behavioral activation, cognitive therapy, and antidepressant medication in the acute treatment of adults with major depression. Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology 74: 658–670. doi: 10.1037/0022-006X.74.4.658.
- Dobson, K. (1989) A meta-analysis of the efficacy of cognitive therapy for depression. Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology 57: 414–419. doi: 10.1037/0022-006X.57.3.414.

- Dobson, K., Hollon, S., Dimidjian, S., Schmaling, K., Kohlenberg, R., Gallop, R., ... Jacobson, N. (2008) Randomized trial of behavioral activation, cognitive therapy, and antidepressant medication in the prevention of relapse and recurrence in major depression. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology* 76: 468–477. doi: 10.1037/0022-006X.76.3.468.
- Driessen E, Hegelmaier LM, Abbass AA. The efficacy of short-term psychodynamic psychotherapy for depression: a meta-analysis update. *Clin Psychol Rev* (2015) 42:1–15. doi:10.1016/j.cpr.2015.07.004
- Edinger, J. & Sampson, W. (2003). A primary care 'friendly' cognitive behavioral insomnia therapy. *SLEEP*, 26, 177–182. Retrieved from www.journalsleep.org/Articles/260209.pdf.
- Eels, T. (1997) *Handbook of Psychotherapy Case Formulation*, New York: Guilford Press.
- "Fennell, M. (1999) *Overcoming Low Self-Esteem: A Self-Help Guide Using Cognitive-Behavioural Techniques*, London: Constable Robinson." ("The key principles of cognitive behavioural therapy") ("The key principles of cognitive behavioral therapy")
- Greenberger, D., Padesky, C. (1995) *Mind Over Mood: A Cognitive Therapy Treatment Manual for Clients*, New York: Guilford Press.
- "Hellman CJ, Budd M, Borysenko J, McClelland DC, Benson H. A study of the effectiveness of two group behavioral medicine interventions for patients with psychosomatic complaints." ("Successful medical and psychological management of recurring chest pain ...") ("Successful medical and psychological management of recurring chest pain ...") *Behav Med*. 1990;16:165–73.
- Johnson JA, Rash JA, Campbell TS, et al. A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials of cognitive behavior therapy for insomnia (CBT-I) in cancer survivors. *Sleep Med Rev* 2016;27:20–8. doi:10.1016/j.smrv.2015.07.001 CrossRefPubMed
- Keefe JR, McCarthy KS, Dinger U, Zilcha-Mano S, Barber JP. A meta-analytic review of psychodynamic therapies for anxiety disorders. *Clin Psychol Rev* (2014) 34:309–23. doi:10.1016/j.cpr.2014.03.004
- "Nakao M, Shinozaki Y, Nolido N, Ahern DK, Barsky AJ." ("(PDF) Randomized controlled trial on the effectiveness of cognitive ...") ("(PDF) Randomized controlled trial on the effect of cognitive ...") *Responsiveness of hypochondriacal patients with chronic low-back pain to cognitive-behavioral therapy. psychosomatics* 2012;53:139–47.
- Schmidt S, Grossman P, Schwarzer B, Jena S, Naumann J, Walach H. Treating fibromyalgia with mindfulness-based

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stress reduction: results from a 3-armed randomized controlled trial. pain. 2011;152:361–9.

Shirotsuki K, Nonaka Y, Takano J, Abe K, Adachi SI, Adachi S, et al. Brief internet-based cognitive behavior therapy program with a supplement drink improved anxiety and somatic symptoms in Japanese workers. Biopsychosoc Med. 2017;11:25.

Verhaak PF, Kerssens JJ, Dekker J, Sorbi MJ, Bensing JM. Prevalence of chronic

benign pain disorder among adults: a review of the literature. pain. 1998;77:231–9.

Wendt J, Hamm AO, Pané-Farré CA, Thayer JF, Gerlach A, Gloster AT, et al. Pretreatment cardiac vagal tone predicts dropout from and residual symptoms after exposure therapy in patients with panic disorder and agoraphobia. Psychother Psychosom 2018;87:187–9.